

Analysis Public Relations Planning and Evaluation of Corporate Social Responsibility Programs (Case Study: The Body Shop)

Idah Wati¹, Afrina Sari²

^{1,2}Master of Communication Science Department, Budi Luhur University, Jakarta, Indonesia

Email address: aidaindah03[DOT]aai[AT]gmail[DOT]com, farina[DOT]sari[AT]budiluhur[DOT]ac[DOT]id

Abstract— Waste in Indonesia reaches 6,000 tons per day, and 13% of plastic waste in one of the Bio-Bag programs is one of The Body Shop Indonesia's Corporate Social Responsibility programs. This program emphasizes environmental issues. The purpose of this research is to find out how the implementation of The Body Shop Indonesia's Public Relations and Corporate Social Responsibility Planning in Campaigning BIO-BAGS the Body Shop Corporate Social Responsibility Program. In this study, researchers used a descriptive analysis method by taking data by interview using this method. The researcher will more easily describe this research. The results of this study are The Body Shop Indonesia's program has contributed to the fight against plastic waste. The campaigns that The Body Shop Indonesia has carried out are Bio-Bag. In this study, researchers hope that this research can provide a new perspective for readers that Corporate Social Responsibility is more than just a corporate social responsibility. It hoped that after reading this research, the reader would arise a desire to jointly protect the environment and participate in the campaigns that will carry out.

Keywords— Corporate Social Responsibility, Evaluation, PENCILS, Plastic Waste, Public Relations.

I. INTRODUCTION

The success of public relations in forming or maintaining an organization's image is the success of a series of complex and relatively long process series. Organizational image manifested in the various components that form it, and each component naturally touches with specific public variations [1]. One of the public relations activities is CSR to provide a positive image of the community. CSR is an understanding of corporate social responsibility, or Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Indonesia continues to experience growth. Rudito and Famiola mentioned that CSR is a need for corporates to be able to interact with local communities as a form of society as a whole [2]. In its existence, Corporate Social Responsibility is one part of the Public Relations (PR) program. In this case, Cutlip, Center, and Broom mentioned that CSR is an embodiment of the role of PR philanthropy as a significant element in the corporate environment. The Corporate Social Responsibility program continues to experience development and innovation in various companies in Indonesia, especially since it stipulated as an obligation stipulated in Chapter V article 74 of Law No. 40 of 2007. Corporate social responsibility is one of the company's commitments to reduce negative images and make positive contributions to stakeholders relating to economic, social, and

environmental aspects for sustainable development [3]. The owners and managers of the company have begun to realize that they also have a social responsibility. To participate in protecting the safety of the environment and the community, so that company management is looking for ways to fulfill these responsibilities, namely by establishing a Public Relations section that is responsible for taking care of that problem [4], how to see the relationship between the corporation and its stakeholders, one of which can see from how the performance of corporate social responsibility (CSR) programs. The high or low performance of CSR programs does not guarantee the merits of the corporate relations of stakeholders, but from this performance, it can see how the commitment, corporate policies, and actions towards their stakeholders or in particular towards the closest community [5]. Today the environment is an issue that needs careful and careful attention — the environment currently threatened by various impacts caused by various human activities. Over the years, the current environment began to show significant changes [6]. Upholding life in the balance of environmental interests requires humans to place themselves as part of the natural environment. A balanced life is one manifestation of the growth of strong faith and an attitude of life orientation to make the earth better [7]. When the environment is getting better, the more balanced the life of human beings, the more open the possibility of developing into a better human being.

Along with population growth and the development of various industries, environmental issues have become a severe problem faced by humans. Environmental pollution is a shared problem. Environmental problems can categorize as local, national, regional, and global environmental problems. The categorization based on the impact of environmental problems, whether the impact is only local, national, regional, or global. When we see the earth as a whole, the earth is a whole system and cannot be separated. Waste can simply interpret as all reliable goods that not used anymore. Often waste creates severe problems if not managed properly — complex waste management with multi-stages. Starting from garbage generated at the household level, industrial waste or agricultural waste, garbage collection, garbage transportation, waste management facilities to the Final Disposal Site (TPA). Garbage must receive serious attention from the agency responsible in each area to prevent or minimize pollution that can cause [8]. Environmental issues have become a global

issue that demands the attention of various parties, both private and government institutions. Many parties have voiced a global commitment to make the environment better through the "go green" campaign that invites the public to be environmentally friendly and make energy savings in various sectors [9]. The condition of the environmental crisis in Indonesia that requires awareness of various parties to take part in act to improve Responses related to environmental issues is more quickly followed up by private companies that are beginning to turn to the concept of "green initiative" to run their business. Like the Body Shop, a well-known cosmetics company founded by Perilli, is a company that is well known today for its Social Responsibility (CSR) implementation. The CSR used by Anita Roddick, the founder of this body shop, is environment-based. The Body Shop is campaigning to save the tropical forests of Brazil and fight for fairer trade rules. It has genuinely dedicated all his soul and company to social activities at home and abroad and also won the Exceptional CSR Practice award at the 12th Annual Business Awards in 2011, this shows that the company is very concerned about CSR in their company. Environment for the better. One of the efforts is by implementing a minimum packaging policy for all its products.

The Body Shop International has used recycled plastic in every packaging of The Body Shop products. To that end, The Body Shop in Indonesia issues Bio-Bagss (shopping bags) that are environmentally friendly because 30% made from cassava flour. The specialty of this Bio-Bags in addition to reducing the use of petroleum, this plastic is also more easily biodegradable, this is also a step forward of The Body Shop in Indonesia to create an environmentally safe company. The Body Shop Indonesia runs its CSR activities through campaigns that The Body Shop has designed by company principles. The campaign aims to promote The Body Shop products but through the Corporate Social Responsibility channel. The campaign is made as attractive as possible by ongoing social issues, aiming that the public can contribute to helping others and caring for the environment in exciting ways. Based on the description above, the researcher would like to see more about the planning and evaluation of The Body Shop PR in managing the BIO-BAGS CSR program. So researchers are interested in researching the Analysis of Public Relations Planning and Evaluation of the BIO-BAGS The Body Shop Corporate Social Responsibility Program. The urgency of this research is to know the planning and evaluation of the BIO-BAGS CSR Program The Body Shop in more detail and further analyze the CSR program at The Body Shop Indonesia outlets. The purpose of this study was to determine how the Implementation of the Public Shop and Corporate Social Responsibility Planning of The Body Shop Indonesia in Campaigning BIO-BAGS the Body Shop Corporate Social Responsibility Program.

II. LITERATURE STUDY

An easy way to comply with the conference paper formatting requirements is to use this document as a template and simply type your text into it.

A. Public Relations & Management Public Relation

According to Jefkins, Public Relations, at its core, always related to the activities of creating understanding through knowledge, and through these activities, it hoped that an impact would appear that is positive change [10]. According to Kasali, Public Relations, is a very strategic approach that uses the concepts of the concept of Public Relations itself according to the IPR (Institute of Public Relations) is the overall effort that is planned and continuous in order to create and maintain good intentions (goodwill) and mutual understanding between an organization and its entire audience [11]. For the life of an organization, communication is essential because, without organizational communication, there is never or died. In organizations, the critical role of Public Relations is abbreviated (PR) as a modern management tool; then, structurally, it is an integral part of an institution or organization. In line with the concept of public relations that is developing now is a concept that emphasizes the importance of two-way communication. According to Howard Childs, the primary function of public relations is not to display the views of the organization or the art of public attitudes, but to make reconciliation or adaptation to each public interest personal aspects of the organization as well as corporate behaviour that have significant social significance. PR helps the organization make adjustments to the environment in which the organization operates [12]. Quite a lot defines Public Relations management from various experts, scientists, and practitioners, the bottom line is that Public Relations management can see conceptually, functionally, and other elements in an institution or organization. The notion of Public Relations management is almost the same as the notion of Public Relations in the sphere of communication. However, in the scope of management, it puts more emphasis on the workings or strategies of a Public Relations practitioner from a worker or employee who is obliged to act like a professional, which ultimately has a specific goal for the institution or organization it represents. Respect, maintain good relations with the internal and external institutions they represent, form, and maintain the positive image of the institution or organization. Cutlip and Center argue that Public Relations can distinguish to management functions through the concept of administrative activities (operating concept of administration) and special staff functions in administrative services (specialized staff function serving administrators) [13]. Public Relations is a management function that assesses public attitudes, identifies organizational policies and procedures in the public interest, and plans a program of activities and communication to gain understanding and support from the public. The role of communication in the management activities of organizations or institutions of today or large companies is usually handed over or carried out by the Public Relations or Public Relations. From the role carried out, the Public Relations Officer or PRO Manager will perform corporate management functions such as Communicator, Relationship, Back-Up Management, Good Image Maker [14].

In practice, Public Relations can double function: on the one hand, as an MPR to achieve Market objective objectives,

while the other party as the main of the company), in creating a positive corporate identity and image (makes identity and corporate image). While the purpose of stakeholder programs, trying to build mutual understanding (Mutual Understanding), mutual respect (Mutual Appreciation). Good Will (Good Will) and tolerance (Tolerance), both internal and external public. CPR (Corporate Public Relations), to achieve Company Goals (this goal also applies to The Body Shop Indonesia, which has been operating for quite a long time in Indonesia, although this company already has a pretty good image and reputation with all campaign programs held, the word of the mouth of the community is not something that can dam. Rumours and issues about The Body Shop Indonesia can emerge anytime, and this step is a step to prevent the emergence of rumours and issues. With the holding of the BIO-BAGS Corporate Body Responsibility program, The Body Shop expected that the company could get the legitimacy of the image and good reputation of the community. In addition to the community, a positive view of the stakeholders is also the essential thing to run the public relations function in management.

B. Corporate Social Responsibility

Cutlip, Center, and Broom explains that "Public Relations is a management function that establishes and maintains an enjoyable and beneficial relationship between an organization and the public that influences the success or failure of the organization [15]. Frazier Moore explains in his book that the public or the primary audience of a company are shareholders, consumers, community or community, distributors, educators, and government. One of the roles held by a public relations company or an organization is to have good relations with the community. One way to be able to relate well with the community is by carrying out Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) activities [16]. H.R Bowen believes that business people should pursue a policy and make decisions or the implementation of CSR activities aimed at fostering good relations with all parties associated with the company as well as to enhance the company's reputation, through mutual relations and gaining trust. CSR activities have a strategic function for the company, which is as part of risk management, especially in establishing social safety valves. By implementing CSR, companies are expected to not only pursue short-term profits but also must contribute to improving the welfare and quality of life of the people and the long-term environment. The benefits of CSR for companies that implement it, namely:

- a. Build and enhance the company's reputation
- b. Improve the company's image
- c. Reduce the company's business risk
- d. Broaden the scope of the company's business
- e. Maintain the company's brand position
- f. Maintain resources quality human beings
- g. Ease of obtaining access to capital
- h. Increasing returns on capital decisions
- i. Increasing returns on critical matters
- j. Obtaining management of risk management

There are benefits to be gained from the implementation of corporate social responsibility, both for the company itself, for

the community, government, and other stakeholders [17]. There are two types of CSR concepts, which are broad and narrow terms. CSR, in a broad sense, is closely related to the goal of achieving sustainable economic activity. The sustainability of economic activities is not only related to social responsibility but also concerns the company's accountability to the community and the nation and the international world. According to Widjaja and Yeremia CSR is a form of collaboration between companies (not only limited liability companies) with all things (stakeholders) that directly or indirectly interact with companies to continue to guarantee the existence and survival of the business (sustainability) Of the company [18]. Understanding the concept of CSR in the business world began with the emergence of stakeholder theory, which provides a different picture of neoclassical theory. Lantos explains that the neoclassical theory talks about the role of a real business to get maximum profit and has low ethical standards and social responsibility towards society. Whereas the view of stakeholder theory assumes that a business is required to have social awareness and must be sensitive to the potential hazards caused by actions about various stakeholders [19]. CSR activities divided into five types, including Cause Promotion, Cause-Related Marketing, Corporate Social Marketing, Community Philanthropy, Community Volunteering, and Socially Responsible Business Practice [20]. As for the stages of CSR itself is divided into three, namely:

- a. Charity, at this stage, the company is motivated to do CSR for religious reasons, traditions, and programs that made have a relatively short period and only overcome the problem for a moment.
- b. Philanthropy At this stage, the company's motivation to carry out CSR is due to norms, ethics, and universal law with a mission to find or overcome the root problems, and the nature of the program is more planned, organized, and programmed.
- c. Corporate Citizenship At this stage, what motivates companies to do CSR is reconciliation with social order so that the company has the awareness to make a real contribution to society, and this program has internalized in company policies.
- d. Based on the understanding of CSR described above, the Bio-Bag Corporate Body Responsibility program is included in the Corporate Citizenship because this program aims to reconcile with social order so that the company has the awareness to make a real contribution to society and this program has been internalized in company policies and start with awareness and concern for the earth and the environment.

III. METHOD

This study uses a qualitative approach, the data collected in the form of words, images, and not numbers and the data that will use as a description of the presentation of the report comes from interview scripts, field notes, photos, videotapes, personal documents, notes or memos, and other official documents. The research method used in this study is the

intrinsic case study method because it focuses on the case itself, namely program evaluation and analysis using the Two-Way Symmetric Model theory. This research uses an intrinsic case study, and the focus is on the case itself because the case presents an unusual or unique situation (eg, evaluating the program) [2]. The object of this research is the Public Relations Division of PT. The Body Shop Indonesia.

The study was conducted by observing how the implementation of PT. Body Shop Indonesia in campaigning for existing programs. Subjects or qualitative research informants targeted. Research objectives do not depend on the title and research topic but concretely illustrated from the formulation of the research problem. In this study, the object under study is Public Relations activities, especially the Corporate Body Responsibility Corporate The Indonesian Shop program in Bio-Bag. The research subjects are informants who are Public Relations Manager, Social and Environmental Values Executive, and Employee Relations Specialist. Furthermore, this study uses the Concept of Four Step Public Relations and the Concept of PENCILS (Publicity, Event, News, Community Investment, Image, Lobbying, and Social Responsibility). The method used in this study is a qualitative method using the Constructivism Paradigm. The difference between the two studies above is that in this study, researchers used CSR experts to strengthen the results of this study, and this study uses concepts related to Public Relations. In Public Relations there is a mix of Public Relations known by the acronym PENCILS including:

- a. Publications: creating news to find publicity that aims to create interest in a person, product, idea, and organization. Through the placement of a story that is beneficial to the mass media. Publicity can have an excellent effect on the public because with publicity the public can know in advance about the company or the product offered if it already knows the interest of the public to find out more about the company or the product offered after that arises the public's perception, and the audience becomes interested in the company or the product offered. It is required to collaborate with the press or journalists, aiming to benefit the image of the institution, company, or organization it represents.
- b. Event (Preparation of the program of events): Designing and making an event or can also be called a special event that has planned. Time, place, date and arrangement of events have been determined in a systematic and orderly manner. The holding of an event provides new information to the public because the event can increase knowledge, awareness, efforts to fulfill tastes, and attract sympathy or empathy to foster mutual understanding for both parties. The purpose of Public Relations holding an event is to obtain a positive image of the community and to form public opinion.
- c. News (Creating news): trying to create news through press releases, newsletters and bulletins, and others. Refers to technical writing 5W + 1H (Who, What, Where, Whom, Why, and How), with the systematic writing of an inverted

pyramid.

- d. Community Involvement (Community care): establishing social contact with specific groups of people or can also be interpreted as jumping directly into the field to interact with people who have the aim of maintaining good relations with the institutions they represent.
- e. Inform and Image (inform and reach the image): in Public Relations, there are two essential functions, namely telling something to the public and making a positive image in the eyes of the public. Both are interrelated, if we share information, insights, new knowledge to the public, then the public will form perception, and that perception forms the opinions and opinions of the public can provide an image or image of the institutions, companies, organizations, products, services represented.
- f. Lobbying and Negotiation (Approach and negotiate): Lobbying is an informal communication activity in order to persuade, seduce, influence other parties so that the other party can approve the proposals, ideas, or ideas of the lobbying actors. Negotiation is a process for submitting and considering offers until an offer is accepted. Moreover, both of these are very necessary for a Public Relations Officer.
- g. Social Responsibility: social responsibility in Public Relations is an essential element because it not only considers the internal scope of an institution, organization, company that it represents but also the concern for the community to achieve success in gaining sympathy from the community so that a positive image can be formed [20].

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Body Shop work ethic inspired by nature; therefore, through the use of natural raw materials to make cosmetic products, The Body Shop believes it can help protect the environment and support its development. It supported by the promotion of The Body Shop to recycle resources, minimize waste and use unnecessary packaging from product packaging, recycle energy, grow plants to absorb carbon produced, and commit to becoming carbon neutral in 2010. On the other hand, The Body Shop always listens to the suggestions of its stakeholders and collaborates with WWF to give attention to oil palm and timber users to protect forests and nature reserves [21]. There are several speakers as a speaker:

- a. First guest speaker named Ratu Ommaya, a woman who was born on December 22, is a graduate of STIKOM The London School of Public Relations. Before working at The Body Shop as a Public Relations Manager for seven years, he worked at PT. Pasaraya Tosersajaya for one year five months as Public Relations and Marketing Communications Executive, then in Matrix Communication as Handling P&G Products for seven months.
- b. The second guest speaker named Dita Agustia, is a graduate from Gadjah Mada University. Before working at The Body Shop as a Social & Environmental Values Executive for four years.
- c. The third speaker, Martinus Kukuh, is a graduate of

Gadjah Mada University. Before occupying his current position as an Employee Relations Specialist for three years, he also held a Social & Environmental Values Executive position for seven years at The Body Shop

A. CSR as a Social Program

Another definition of CSR, according to Ismail Solihin, is "one of the forms of corporate responsibility towards stakeholders." CSR in the book Gunawan Widjaja and Yeremia Ardi Pratama in his book entitled "Legal Risk & Corporate Business Without CSR," has not defined CSR by their own opinion, but in the book defining CSR refers to the contents of Article 1 Item 3 of the Company Law, where that TJSL is an obligation. There is also a mention that CSR is a mechanism for a company to voluntarily integrate attention to the social environment into its operations and interactions with stakeholders, which exceeds social responsibility in the field of law. Therefore, it becomes natural for The Body Shop in Indonesia to conduct women's empowerment programs, both through collaboration with several women's empowerment institutions and through various campaign activities such as "No Need to Be Slim and White to Be Happy" and others. The Body Shop wants to be "A Brand that Stands for Women." Therefore, in selling its products, The Body Shop hopes that the customer is not wrong to spend his money and knows full well that the money he bought is commensurate with the money spent. The priority of The Body Shop social programs in Indonesia is also to protect (save their future) the future of children, who often become secondary victims after women during disasters or domestic violence. For this, in collaboration with Children on The Edge Foundation UK, The Body Shop Indonesia has built and routinely supported the operational costs of the Women's and Children's Empowerment Center in Neuheun village, Aceh Besar District, Banda Aceh. Besides, The Body Shop in Indonesia, in collaboration with the Centro Lifestyle Department Store, financed the rebuilding as well as aiding costs for 3 (three) years at Patuk State Elementary School, Yogyakarta, which collapsed due to the earthquake disaster.

The Body Shop is always trying to make social and environmental changes for the better. One effort is to implement a minimum packaging policy for all its products. The Body Shop International has used recycled plastic in every package of The Body Shop products. To that end, The Body Shop in Indonesia issues Bio-Bagss (shopping bags) that are environmentally friendly because 30% made from cassava flour. The specialty of this Bio-Bags, in addition to reducing the use of petroleum, this plastic is also more readily biodegradable. The Body Shop is always trying to make social and environmental changes for the better. One effort is to implement a minimum packaging policy for all its products. The emotional connection to be achieved through the program is nothing but a manifestation of The Body Shop's efforts in Indonesia in managing consumers. Besides, there is another program from The Body Shop in Indonesia that also engages consumers through the value of purchasing purchases from The Body Shop products for causes related to women, namely through the "Share for Women-Together Sharing Power"

campaign. Forms of consumer management through this program aims to create and retain loyal consumers.

B. Interview Result CSR Program

As an activity, both practical and strategic, the implementation of CSR must be through careful planning. This planning done because the implementation of CSR certainly involves the cost, time, and mobilization of human resources that will have an impact on company activities. The results obtained are as follows:

- a. Guest speaker Ratu Ommaya explained, "His awareness is one thing that a decent place to live for humans is only on earth. Anita Roddick has always been a visionary businessman and environmental activist. In the past, there has not been a change in climate or anything, but he is already starting to think. If this earth exploited irresponsibly one day, it would be destroyed and exhausted; one day, it will change. That is one basis for what a great business and high profit [22] if it turns out that where we stand and sell, this will eventually someday destroyed and extinct. So that is one of the main points that must save where we live, so everyone must be concerned." The Protect Our Planet Program is highly prioritized because in the current environmental damage in the world is getting worse, people are starting to ignore the environment even though the health of the earth is a fertile and well-maintained environment. The more manicured and fertile the healthier the earth, and vice versa, if the more damage to the environment, the earth will become sick and continue to cause disasters that will cause considerable losses to humans.
- b. Speaker Martinus Kukuh explained, "Protect Our Planet becomes an advantage for us in Indonesia, the body shop is desperately fighting for it because we have a lot of environmental damage and the body shop wants to invite people to take care of it. Then protect our planet is purely concerned with individuals; whoever means not just an internal body shop. It became an essential program to be discussed. Real proof that has done in Jakarta, one of them in body shop shops called to bring back our bottle, if the contents finished, please return the body shop bottles and get points. Furthermore, we never use Styrofoam because it cannot parse forever. And there is a free from plastic campaign, we encourage the government to make regulations all retail companies sell the plastic to the people I am thinking of buying. So, the body shop encourages the government to make regulations selling plastic bags, so plastic bags are not given away free. If the body shop no longer used, we use a paper bag. In Indonesia, the Protect Our Planet Program is highly prioritized, as we have seen that much environmental damage has occurred in Indonesia, and public awareness of the environment has declined. That is why The Body Shop Indonesia carries out campaigns based on the Protect Our Planet program such as, Bio-Bags 'and encourages the government to make a breakthrough that is very important to combat environmental damage by reducing the use of plastic bags, plastic bags are not provided free of charge

but must pay. As a large multinational company, The Body Shop is committed to fighting climate change due to global warming. Global warming with a variety of efforts can at least reduce the impact caused. The Body Shop's efforts to use energy in outlets and offices throughout the world, the use of recycled plastic bottles by utilizing bottles made from PET (polyethylene terephthalate), replacing shopping bags with recycled materials, and can decompose soil. CSR program planning is more circular, such as a cycle that starts from A-B-C and will end to A. four main activities have been carried out by The Body Shop Indonesia, namely the selection of issues, selection of activities, development, and implementation of programs and evaluation. The results of this evaluation will, of course, used as a basis for planning further CSR programs.

C. Evaluation CSR Program

Every Public Relations (PR) program certainly needs parameters to determine the success or failure of the program [23]. The parameter becomes essential for marketers to ensure that the PR budget not wasted. As quoted answers from the guest speaker Ms. Ratu Ommaya: "For brands, there are some essential things that must be determined at the beginning when you have to make a PR program. Namely, the objectives of a program, target audience or market, and expected output. After that, new strategies and action plans can make ". According to Ratu Ommaya, the aim of The Body Shop as a brand in each of its PR programs is to provide not just information, but also a means of public education, both in terms of programs for beauty products or social-environmental campaigns. From the business side, he said, every PR program carried out also aims to strengthen the brand image and reputation. Thus, more and more public awareness of the movement of The Body Shop will undoubtedly affect business performance. The guest speaker also expressed the same thing. According to Martinus, according to him, the essential brand today would depend on the results of the audit of the brand. Starting from the most basic scale, brands need awareness, increasing brand preference, brand usage, to brand sales performance. In designing its PR programs, The Body Shop involves external parties, both for small scale to large scale programs. The following quote from Mr. Martinus Kuku: "Because, for the most part, it can even say that almost all PR stakeholders are related to external matters. Moreover, the PR program at The Body Shop not directly linked to the sales target. " The Body Shop always makes goals in a year that will reveal through several PR programs. That is why The Body Shop PR program is not a program that runs alone. There are two measurement tools for The Body Shop PR program. First, it is quantitative with measurement of media coverage value up to how many people read news about the program — or commonly called Opportunity to See (media circulation). As for Digital PR (social media channel) programs, the measurement tools can see from the number of impressions achieved, the number of likes, and comments. The second measuring instrument is qualitative. Following the statement Ms. Ratu Ommaya: "Each program we see the output whether positive, neutral, or negative tone." The resource person Ms.

Dita Agustia added, through social media, both CSR activities or product sales processes. It is done to make it easier for customers to get closer to The Body Shop. The utilization of social media properly will help the success of the organization of a company's activities. Social media is an excellent vehicle for carrying and spreading the message of an image, brand, or service to millions of cyberspace consumers. Besides helping in promotion, social media also provides its advantages in managing CSR activities or public relations activities. Social media brings new perspectives and patterns in the information age in the form of technology networks that allow anyone to access anywhere to meet their needs. Organizations or companies that adopt the internet or social media will experience rapid development during the information society Interview with Ratu Ommaya Public Relations Manager, in the Body Shop office, which is increasingly heterogeneous and can whittle the target audience or a more significant number of markets. As stated by the guest speaker Ms. Dita Agustia follows; "Social media that are often used by TBSI are Twitter, Facebook, Youtube, Instagram. Twitter and Instagram are more directed than SMS and Instastory. It is because Twitter has restrictions on the content. With twitter, the information obtained is faster. Twitter can be much faster and broader in terms of message dissemination capabilities. As well as Facebook or other social media that have been implemented by TBSI ". Based on the results of the study, it can see that TBSI is actively conducting customer engagement, which has successfully involved customers in activities or conversation through social media, especially activities related to Protect Our Planet. Some of its activities are Bio-Bags, which is a program that invites us to return empty packages of The Body Shop products that will be collected, and the results of their processing used for community empowerment. As stated by the guest speaker Ms. Ratu Ommaya follows; "Bio-Bag is an educational program for consumers and the public to be responsible for plastic packaging products that have been used every day by not adding waste deposits in the surrounding environment or landfills (TPA), The Body Shop donates Rp1,000 for each Bio transaction Bag to Indonesia Diet Plastic Bags. Bio-Bags also has Clean Up Jakarta Day aims to increase awareness and sensitivity to the dangers of littering and the importance of the recycling process - starting with ourselves, at home or work. More than 350 volunteers from The Body Shop went to Gelora Bung Karno Stadion to clean Jakarta together. In about 1 hour, The Body Shop collected more than 500 kg of trash from the area around Plaza Utara, GBK Stadium. Waste collected is then transported by DKI Jakarta Sanitation Department. This waste, together with nearly 100 tons of waste from 37 locations throughout the Greater Jakarta area, including two locations in Tangerang that participated in the Clean Up Jakarta Day 2015, was recycled to the Jakarta Waste Bank. Environmental issues are being intensively discussed in the media in 2015, especially the mass media online media incessantly publishing news about environmental issues. The environmental issue discussed is about waste. Based on Jambeck data (2015), Indonesia is ranked second in the world, producing plastic waste to the sea, which reached 187.2

million tons after China, which reached 262.9 million tons. According to InSWA (Indonesia Solid Waste Association), the amount of plastic waste reaches 14% of total production. Plastic waste is rubbish that is difficult to decompose, making the soil polluted if disposed of improperly will clog waterways that can cause flooding. The loss will increase if plastic waste continues to be produced and used daily for various purposes. Awareness of the dangers of plastic waste must be immediately brought to the surface so that people do not inefficiently use for unnecessary things that will later waste. Strict regulations from the government must enforce so that plastic rubbish can be reduced. Not only the responsibility of the community but all parties, one of which the company must take part in fighting this environmental issue. The role of a company to combat environmental issues can be seen from the company's CSR activities. The Body Shop is one of the companies that aggressively conduct CSR, the Body Shop CSR program that promotes environmental problems is the Bio-Bags Program, as evidenced by the campaigns carried out by The Body Shop Indonesia in combating the problem of plastic waste. To find out how the implementation of CSR The Body Shop Program "Protect Our Planet," researchers used the concept of Four Step Public Relations and PENCILS Concepts in studying this research. The following are the field findings that the researchers have systematically compiled based on the concepts used:

- a. Problems: from the findings on the ground that underlies the "Protect Our Planet & Bio-Bag" campaign, environmental damage is getting worse, and human consciousness about the environment is decreasing. Humans, as subjects in the utilization of natural resources, have a significant role in forming a society that is friendly to the environment and is required to have a concern for the preservation of nature and the environment and respect for other existences on this earth. In this study, researchers wanted to increase further public awareness of the importance of protecting the environment well. Because of the lack of vigilance and sensitivity of the community to littering.
- b. Planning: after discovering the facts, the next step is to plan, which is to plan activities related to the Protect Our Planet programs, such as Bio-Bag and Green Month Campaign. TBSI manages plastic waste through the concept of reduce-reuse-recycle, such as utilizing used plastic bottles from The Body Shop products. The used bottles recycled into useful items such as brooches and containers for storing accessories. In the Clean Up Jakarta activity. The aim is to increase awareness and sensitivity to the dangers of littering and the importance of the recycling process - starting with ourselves, at home, or at work. Likewise, with the Green Month activities. All activities carried out are related to the environment. Through this activity, The Body Shop Indonesia will educate customers to contribute to the environment for a more comfortable life. Plans that have been prepared well as a result of careful thought based on the facts and data available, then communicated or carried out operational activities.
- c. Communication: plans that have appropriately prepared as a result of careful thought based on the facts and data available are then communicated or carried out activities or programs. With conducting a Protect Our Planet program campaign, such as Bio-Bags, clean up Jakarta and the Green Month Campaign expected to increase public awareness of the environment, because the aim is education to make people aware of the change. However, TBSI does not always target the public widely; the first time educated the employees internally first. So it starts with employees to new customers to the public. Because later that will campaign to the public from the public itself
- d. Evaluating: based on research conducted by researchers, at this stage, found activities that support the Protect Our Planet programs such as Bio-Bags, Clean Up Jakarta, and Green Month. The purpose of this activity is to provide public education, both in terms of programs for beauty products or environmental, social campaigns. From the business side, he said, every PR program carried out also aims to strengthen the brand image and reputation. Thus, more and more public awareness of the movement of The Body Shop will undoubtedly affect business performance. Starting from the most basic scale, brands need awareness, increasing brand preference, brand usage, to brand sales performance. In designing its PR programs, The Body Shop involves external parties, both for small scale to large scale programs. There are two measurement tools for The Body Shop PR program. First, it is quantitative with measurement of media coverage value up to how many people read news about the program or commonly called Opportunity To See (media circulation). As for Digital PR (social media channel) programs, the measurement tools can be seen from the number of impressions achieved, the number of likes, and comments. The second measurement tool is qualitative in that each program can see its output, whether positive, neutral, or negative tone. Concerning data collection, he added, for digital PR such as social media, then the data can be taken from each post how many retweets, likes, comments, including counting his impressions.

D. PENCILS Analysis

In addition to using the four steps in this study also used the PENCILS concept as a basis for conducting research, include:

- a. Publications: marketing communication conducted by The Body Shop Indonesia at its outlets or stores done through visual merchandising, posters, leaflets, and special offers. The Body Shop Sales are active in offering their products to customers who are shopping at outlets. Not only customers who are shopping, but TBSI also publishes through social media, both CSR activities or product sales processes. It is done to make it easier for customers to get closer to The Body Shop. The utilization of social media well will help the success of the organization of a company's activities.
- b. Event: based on the research results of the event conducted by TBSI in the Protect Our Planet program, it can help economic value for the community and will not stop here

to continue to educate all parties: starting from The Body Shop staff and partners, customers and the public to take concrete action in reducing plastic bags and rubbish. And 3R awareness: Reduce-Reuse-Recycle for a better Jakarta and Indonesia Free of Trash 2020. The event that held was also responded positively by the community, such as Bring Back Our Bottle, many customers participated in this activity. Because TBSI educates the public to be responsible for plastic packaging products that have been used daily by not adding to the pile of garbage in the surrounding environment or landfills.

- c. News: as a cosmetics and body care company, The Body Shop cannot be separated from the role and influence of the media, especially beauty and lifestyle magazines. As a brand that rarely advertises in the mass media, The Body Shop is media coverage as a powerful weapon to inform consumers about everything related to their brand. Media coverage is so sufficient because that is where the role and sound of the magazine stated. Without tendentious advertisements or advertisements, or paid reviews such as product and advertorial advertisements. Media coverage includes suggestions and information for readers from a media perspective.
- d. Community Involvement: The Body Shop (TBS) was successful because of the right positioning. Unlike other cosmetic brands that always campaign for product benefits. The Body Shop positioned as an environmentally friendly product. During the increasingly crowded competition of the cosmetics industry, both by classic brands and new brands, The Body Shop's differentiation increasingly stands out and is believed by its loyalists. To care for their loyalty, since 2009, The Body Shop Indonesia has cooperated with dozens of communities and non-profit organizations that have a vision and mission in line with the protect our planet program. Especially those related to social, environmental, and humanitarian issues. To date, 15 communities work together and receive support from TBS Indonesia.
- e. Lobbying: In this strategy, The Body Shop invites all of its customers to support and sign the # Pay4Plastic petition that already exists in all The Body Shop stores starting from March 26 to May 2015 or through online www.change.org/dietkantongplastik Petition titled —President and Governor, Make Plastic Bag Diet Regulations addressed to President Joko Widodo.
- f. Social Investment.: TBSI's concern and sensitivity to the environment and social issues in the community, TBSI established The Body Shop Foundation as their Charity program with a focus on human rights and protection of animals and the environment.

V. CONCLUSION

From the research conducted by researchers on The Body Shop Indonesia's Corporate Social Responsibility Program Protect Our Plane such as Bio-Bag to find out how the Implementation of the Protect BIO-BAGS program by using the concept of Four Step Public Relations and PENCILS Concepts, researchers produce a conclusion that is the result of

the analysis and interpretation of researchers alone. Then the researchers concluded the results of the study as follows: The Body Shop Indonesia Corporate Social Responsibility, The BIO-BAGS program, is a program that promotes environmental issues. Bio-Bags made because of the reduced human awareness of environmental problems and our Earth must be protected and preserved because that is the source of human life. The Protect Our Planet program has been inspired by nature; the key to a prosperous nature is a healthy environment. Therefore, The Body Shop in the Bio-Bags program. The highly focused environment, such as reducing waste and minimizing the use of packaging products, planting plants aimed at making the Earth greener and caring for the Earth so that it not exploited irresponsibly. The Body Shop program is planning itself through four main activities, namely the selection of issues, the selection of activities, development, and Implementation.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ike Devi Sulistyningtyas, "Riset sebagai Ujung Tombak Keberhasilan Program Public Relations," *Ilmu Komun.*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 171–186, 2010.
- [2] Ruth Carissa Harianto, "Evaluasi Program Corporate Social Responsibility 'Organic Integrated System' PT. Pembangunan Jawa-Bali Unit Pembangunan Paiton," *J. E-KOMUNIKASI*, vol. 4, no. 1, 2016.
- [3] D. Kartini, *Corporate Social Responsibility Transformasi Konsep Sustainability Management dan Implementasi di Indonesia*. Bandung: Refika Aditama, 2009.
- [4] Morissan, *Teori Komunikasi: Individu Hingga Massa, Edisi Pertama*. Jakarta: Kencana. Mulyana, 2014.
- [5] Dody Prayogo, "Evaluasi Program Corporate Social Responsibility Dan Community Development Pada Industri Tambang Dan Migas," *Makara, Sos. Hum.*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 43–58, 2011.
- [6] Puspita, I. Hartono, L. Ibrahim, and Djoko, "Influence of The Behavior of Citizens Residing in Riverbanks to The Decrease of Water Quality in The River of Karang Anyar Tarakan City," *Mns. DAN Lingkungan.*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 249–258, 2016.
- [7] E. Salim, *Lingkungan Hidup dan Pembangunan*. Jakarta: Mutiara, 2005.
- [8] W. A. Fajar and Dewi Piana, "Sosialisasi Bahaya Membuang Sampah Sembarangan Dan Menentukan Lokasi Tpa Di Dusun Deles Desa Jagonayan Kecamatan Ngablak," *J. Inov. dan Kewirausahaan*, vol. 3, no. 1, 2014.
- [9] Muntadliroh, "The Analysis Of A Strategic Approach To Environmental Public Relations: The Implementation Study Of Green Public Relations Concept," *Penelit. Komun. dan Opini Publik*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 151–164, 2015.
- [10] Jenkins Frank, *Pengantar Public Relations*. Jakarta: Erlangga, 2015.
- [11] R. Kasali, *Manajemen Public Relations.* Jakarta: Graffiti, 2012.
- [12] Service Imelda Nubatonis, "Peran Public Relation Dalam Program Larasita Badan Pertanahan Kabupaten Timor Tengah Utara Di Kelurahan Kefa Tengah," *J. Interak.*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 62–72, 2015.
- [13] A. H. Cutlip, S. M, & Center, *Effective public relation (5thed)*. New Jersey: Prentice-Hall, 1982.
- [14] R. Ruslan, *Manajemen Public Relations & Media Komunikasi*. Jakarta: PT Raja grafindo Persada, 2012.
- [15] S. M. Cutlip, Center, Allen H, and G. M. Broom, *Effective Public Relations*. Edisi Kesembilan. (Jakarta: Kencana), 2009.
- [16] F. Moore, *Hubungan Masyarakat Prinsip, Kasus, dan Masalah*. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya, 2010.
- [17] I. Solihin, *Corporate Social Responsibility: From Charity to Sustainability*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat, 2014.
- [18] G. B. Nayenggita, S. T. Raharjo, and R. Resnawaty, "Praktik Corporate Social Responsibility (Csr) Di Indonesia.," *J. Pekerj. Sos.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 61–66, 2019.
- [19] V. Estriana and U. Wahid, "Erving Goffman's Approach in Perspective and Self-presentation of Transgender in Tambun Bekasi," *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Publications*, vol. 2, no. 2,

- pp. 71–77, 2019.
- [20] Somad, Rismi, Priansa, and Donni, *Manajemen Komunikasi Mengembangkan Bisnis Berorientasi Pelanggan*. Bandung: Alfabeta, 2014.
- [21] Philip kotler. and Gray Armstrong., *Prinsip-prinsip Pemasaran*. Jakarta: Erlangga, 2005.
- [22] I. Ranggadara, G. Wang, and E. R. Kaburuan, “Applying Customer Loyalty Classification with RFM and Naïve Bayes for Better Decision Making,” in *2019 International Seminar on Application for Technology of Information and Communication (iSemantic)*, 2019, pp. 564–568.
- [23] D. A. Roddick, “Building For The Future,” *The Body Shop*, pp. 1–58, 2014.